

Comparative Analysis of Energy Deposition Models in Serpent, CASMO5, and VESTA for a Gd_2O_3 -Loaded Fuel Assembly

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ABSTRACT

This work presents a depletion analysis of a PWR-type fuel assembly with 3.5 wt.% ^{235}U enrichment and 36 gadolinium burnable absorber rods. The simulations were performed with the neutronic codes Serpent, CASMO5, and VESTA, covering a depletion range from 0 to 60 MWd/kgU. The analysis aims to quantify and characterize the reactivity effects associated with the different energy deposition models available in these codes. In addition, other sensitivity analysis that play a key role during depletion were also evaluated. The results indicate that the main discrepancies arise from the estimation of the indirect energy contribution, dominated by neutron capture reactions, with the most significant differences observed during the burnable absorbers depletion phase and at high burnups, with reactivity differences between 400-600 pcm. While this work highlights these differences, further analysis are required to determine which methodology provides the most accurate representation.

Keywords: Serpent, CASMO5, VESTA, Energy Deposition, KERMA, Burnup

1. INTRODUCTION

The main motivation of this work is to characterize and quantify typical reactivity differences that arise during a 2D depletion analysis of a fuel assembly (FA) with burnable absorbers (BAs) when using different models to account for the recoverable energy released per fission event as implemented in the neutronic codes CASMO5, Serpent, and VESTA. For the analysis, a 17x17 PWR-type FA with 3.5 wt.% enrichment and containing 36 *Gd* BA rods with 8 wt.% Gd_2O_3 concentration, was selected. The FA belongs to the Small Modular Reactor (SMR) core design known as PRATIC, developed by the French Atomic Energy and Alternative Energy Commission (CEA) within the framework of the Euratom EASI-SMR project [1, 2], in which this work is partially embedded and carried out as exploratory research. The work is structured as follows. First, a theoretical review of energy deposition models implemented in each code is presented. Second, common modelling assumptions are defined to establish reference base cases, and preliminary sensitivity studies are performed. Finally, the energy deposition models available in each code are compared, and the resulting discrepancies are discussed.

2. RECOVERABLE ENERGY PER FISSION

The amount of energy released per fission event depends on the nucleus to be fissioned and the incident neutron energy. For a ^{235}U the total energy release per fission event is approximately 200 MeV.

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Part of this energy (around 12 MeV) is carried out of the core by antineutrinos and is therefore not recoverable. In addition, neutrons produced during this event are captured by other materials in the core (e.g. coolant, cladding, and BAs), leading to additional decay energy release (between 3-12 MeV) that is deposited into the core. Quantifying this recoverable energy is a burnup-dependent problem is particularly challenging, since the material composition changes over time, affecting capture reaction rates, and new fissile isotopes, such as ^{239}Pu , are produced. This recoverable energy, originated per fission event for a nuclide i , can therefore be expressed as the sum of two components. The first component represents the direct energy contribution, which includes the kinetic energy of fission fragments ($E_{FR,i}$), the kinetic energy of prompt and delayed fission neutrons ($E_{NP,i}$, $E_{ND,i}$), the total energy of prompt and delayed gammas ($E_{GP,i}$, $E_{GD,i}$), and the total energy released by beta particles ($E_{B,i}$), while excluding the energy by antineutrinos. The second component represents the indirect energy contribution (E_{capt}), which mainly arises from neutron capture reactions in other materials present in the core.

By default, Serpent [3] considers a constant recoverable energy (also referred to as energy deposition) value of $H_{235} = 202.27$ MeV/fission for ^{235}U (**edep 0** mode). This value represents the total energy deposited per fission in a typical light-water reactor, and already includes the additional energy released from capture reactions. For other fissile isotopes (e.g., those produced during depletion) Serpent scales this value according to $H_i = \frac{Q_i}{Q_{235}} H_{235}$, where Q_i is the fission Q -value for isotope i . Constant recoverable energy values, which includes implicitly the indirect contribution, are also used in the VESTA code [4]. In Serpent **edep 1** mode, the individual direct energy contribution components ($E_{FR,i}$, $E_{NP,i}$, $E_{ND,i}$, $E_{GP,i}$, $E_{GD,i}$, $E_{B,i}$) are obtained directly from the ENDF/B-VII.1 MT458 data. In this mode, the additional secondary energy released from capture reactions is specified in the input by the user. This specified energy remains constant during a depletion calculation, which is generally not realistic. Similar to edep 0, this mode assumes that all the energy is deposited at the fission sites, i.e., within the fuel material. Mode **edep 2** improves the spatial distribution of energy deposition. Instead of depositing all the energy at the fission sites, neutrons release energy progressively along their interactions in various reactions, while the energy of secondary photons is deposited locally at the corresponding reaction sites. Heating rates from reactions other than fission are calculated using KERMA (Kinetic Energy Release in Materials) coefficients, which also automatically accounts for the secondary energy component released from capture reactions. Finally, **edep 3** extends the capabilities of mode 2 by adding explicit photon transport, allowing a more accurate representation of gamma-ray propagation and energy deposition. Further details on the different Serpent energy deposition modes can be found in [5].

Similar to Serpent edep 1, CASMO5 relies on ENDF/B MF1 MT458 data [6] to account for the direct energy contribution, but it adopts a different approach to model the indirect contribution. By default, CASMO5 uses the ERF2 mode, which assumes a constant value of 5.991 MeV per capture reaction, typical for standard light-water applications. This value, expressed in [MeV/capture], remains constant throughout depletion and is scaled by the burnup-dependent ratio between the total neutron capture rate and the total fission rate to obtain its contribution in [MeV/fission]. In addition to ERF2, CASMO5 provides the ERF0 mode, which offers a more problem-specific method to calculate the energy contribution from capture reactions. Further details on the methodology can be found in [7]. Table I summarizes how each of these components contributing to the total deposited energy is treated in the respective codes and model options.

3. BASE SIMULATION SETUP AND PRELIMINARY ANALYSIS

As mentioned in the introduction, the selected case study is a 17x17 PWR-type loaded with 36 Gd BA rods, see Figure 1. The burnup simulations were performed from 0 to 60 MWd/kgU at specific power of 24.73 W/g. Table II summarizes the base settings selected for the initial comparisons. These are known as the base cases. These settings were defined after several sensitivity studies and based on our best knowledge of the tools, ensuring that the assumptions were made as consistent as possible across the different codes in order to enable fair comparisons. To exploit the symmetry of the FA, only one-

Table I. Energy deposition models summary.

Code and model	Direct energy contribution						Indirect contribution
	EFR _i	EB _i	EGP _i	EGD _i	ENP _i	END _i	E _{capt}
CASMO5 ERF0	ENDF MF1 MT458						lattice/burnup dependent based on capture reactions
CASMO5 ERF2	ENDF MF1 MT458						Constant 5,991 MeV/capture
VESTA	Constant values that include the indirect contribution [4]						
SERPENT edep 0	Constant values that include the indirect contribution						
SERPENT edep 1	ENDF MF1 MT458						User defined
SERPENT edep 2	ENDF MF1 MT458			KERMA coefficients			
SERPENT edep 3	ENDF MF1 MT458	KERMA coefficients + analog photon heat deposition tally					

eighth of the FA was modelled. Radial subdivisions of 1 for UO₂ pellets and 10 for BA pellets were considered, defining, for the one-eighth domain, 32 and 70 depletion zones, respectively. As shown in Table II, the depletion steps were fixed for all codes and managed by CASMO5, resulting in a total of 50 depletion steps, with shorter steps applied during the depletion of the BAs. As part of the preliminary study, several sensitivity analysis (SAs) that could affect the depletion behavior, beyond the impact of the different energy deposition models, were evaluated individually in each code, in addition to the base cases defined in Table II.

Figure 1. One fourth of the 3.5% PRACTIC's FA with 36 BA rods generated by Serpent.

In CASMO5, the following modifications were evaluated: **(1)** replacing default JENDL-4.0 ²³⁹Pu cross section to ENDF/B-VII.1 (*REP 94239 / 'E7R1'*), **(2)** extending the depletion chains (*EXT*), **(3)** disabling the default fission yield adjustment on Rh-109 (*OFF 'YIE1'*), and **(4)** disabling default fission yield adjustment on Mo-103 (*OFF 'YIE2'*) [8]. Figure 2-(a) presents the corresponding k_{∞} for the base case and differences due to the sensitivities. Replacing the ²³⁹Pu cross sections with ENDF/B-VII.1 data and turning off the fission yield adjustment *YIE1* each lead to approximately 200 pcm lower reactivity at 60 MWd/kgU compared to the CASMO5 base case, while extending the depletion chains and turning off *YIE2* result in differences smaller than 25 pcm, i.e., negligible. For the comparisons presented hereafter, the CASMO5 base case including *REP*, *EXT*, and *OFF YIE1* is adopted as the reference solution for further comparisons, and will be referred to simply as the CASMO5 solution.

For the Serpent preliminary SAs, two studies were performed. The first SA consisted of increasing the number of particle histories and inactive cycles in the Serpent base case, while the second SA investigated the impact of alternative burnup predictor/corrector (P/C) algorithms. The first SA was performed increasing the total amount of particle histories up to 2×10^8 with 400 inactive cycles. The results fluctuate symmetrically around zero within a band of ± 20 pcm as shown Figure 2-(b), with no systematic deviations observed, suggesting that the number of particles histories used in the base case is sufficient to accurately characterize the FA during depletion.

Table II. Summary of selected modelling parameters for CASMO5, Serpent, and VESTA. The following settings define the base cases for further sensitivities. Default settings are indicated with (D).

Parameter	CASMO5	SERPENT	VESTA (MCNP6.1/Phoenix)
Code version	3.04.00	2.2.1	2.2.0
Data libraries	e7r1.202.586.bin	endfb71.edep	ENDF/B-VII.1
Coolant temperature [K]	573	573	573
Scat. Thermal library for H-H2O	-	interpolation 550K - 600K	ENDF/B-VIII.0 @573K
Coolant density [g/cm^3]	0.72683	0.72683	0.72683
Fuel temperature [K]	743	743	743
Other materials temperature [K]	573	573	573
Material composition	From Serpent .out	[2]	[2]
Boundary conditions	Reflective	Reflective	Reflective
Domain	1/8	1/8	1/8
Energy groups	95	Continuous	Continuous
Pn-scattering order	3	-	-
Histories	-	pop 1e5 500 100	-
Depletion steps	DEP -60	Same as CASMO5	Same as CASMO5
Power density [kW/g]	24.73e-3	24.73e-3	24.73e-3
Burnup predictor/corrector	Yes (D)	CE/LI (D)	Projected P/C
UO ₂ -Gd ₂ O ₃ rings subdivision	10	10	10
UO ₂ rings division	1	1	1
Energy deposition model	ERF 0	0 (D)	ORIGEN [4]
Isomeric branching ratios	(D)	constant (D) from JEFF-3.1.1	energy-dependent from ENDFB7.1
Depletion solver	CRAM order 14 (D)	CRAM order 14 (D)	Runge-Kutta
No thermal expansion	THE 0	-	-
Effective Doppler temperature	OFF 'DOP'	-	-
Resonance upscatter model	OFF (D)	-	-
Resonance probability tables	-	OFF (D)	YES

Figure 2. (a) CASMO5 base case k_{∞} result and reactivity differences due to the sensitivity analysis. Differences are relative to CASMO5 base case. (b) Serpent base case reactivity difference increasing the amount of particle histories from 50M with 100 inactive cycles to 200M with 400 inactive cycles.

Higher order P/C methods available in Serpent, namely default CE/LI (Constant Extrapolation / Linear Interpolation), LE/LI (Linear Extrapolation/Linear Interpolation), and LE/QI (Linear Extrapolation / Quadratic Interpolation) were evaluated and compared. Figure 3-(a) shows the corresponding reactivity differences. At higher burnup levels, all Serpent methods exhibit a similar trend, with deviations reaching up to approximately 600 pcm lower than CASMO5, whereas VESTA remains closer to CASMO5, within about 200 pcm.

The most notable discrepancies among the Serpent P/C methods occur during the depletion of the BAs,

Figure 3. (a) CASMO5 reference case k_∞ and corresponding reactivity differences. (b-c) Atomic densities and relative differences for the main gadolinium isotopes. All differences are relative to the CASMO5 reference case.

where differences of up to around 400 pcm are observed between the CE/LI and LE/LI approaches. For the selected burnup steps, the LE/* predictor schemes tend to deplete the BAs faster than default CE/LI, as shown in Figure 3-(b-c), which explains the observed reactivity differences. These results indicate that even shorter burnup steps may be required to achieve better consistency between the methods.

The Serpent CE/LI, CASMO5, and VESTA employ, in principle, similar predictor schemes, all based on constant extrapolation. However, the implementation of the corrector step differs among the codes, resulting in variations in how reaction rates and isotopic compositions are evaluated. If possible, readers are referred to the respective code documentation for further details; however, in some cases, only brief descriptions of the methodologies were available, and more information, particularly on algorithm implementation, is needed to fully understand the differences. Based on the results, one may conclude that Serpent CE/LI and CASMO5 have similar P/C schemes, as indicated by the close agreement during the BA depletion phase, although CASMO5 applies a quadratic model to track only gadolinium BA chains, which may also contribute to some differences. Meanwhile, VESTA results are more consistent with the Serpent LE/LI and LE/QI approaches. While a more detailed analysis could be performed, it lies beyond the primary scope of the present work.

4. ANALYSIS OF ENERGY DEPOSITION MODELS

The previous section already presented some results using selected energy deposition models, namely edep 0 for Serpent, ERF0 for CASMO5, and ORIGEN-based model for VESTA. In this section, additional available energy deposition models are tested and discussed. Due to the large number of cases defined for Serpent, the analysis begins by defining and comparing only Serpent cases, some of which employ the same energy deposition model. For example, an additional case was performed for edep 0 with modified heat deposition H_i values. The H_i values considered for this case were extracted directly from the CASMO5 reference case .cax file and listed in Table III. These modified heat deposition values are included using the *set fissh* option in Serpent, replacing the default $H_i = \frac{Q_i}{Q_{235}} H_{235}$ described in section 2. For edep 1, a value of 11.0 MeV/fission was considered for E_{capt} to achieve, on average, a similar energy deposition to the one obtained with CASMO5, as will be showed later. For edep modes 2 and 3, the energy deposition from reactions other than fission is corrected when the system is not critical using the *set edepkcorr* option in Serpent, which is enabled by default. According to the Serpent wiki, the proper functioning of the implementation of this correction is currently under investigation, and disabling it is currently recommended. In this study, results with and without the correction are presented for completeness.

Table III. Constant heat deposition values H_i [MeV/fission] obtained from the CASMO5 reference case .cax file.

Isotope	H_i								
U-235	202.3	Pu-241	213.6	Pu-238	208.7	Cm-245	213.9	Cm-248	216.9
U-236	201.9	Pu-242	211.9	Am-241	213.6	Pa-231	207.7	Cf-249	213.9
Np-237	205.8	Th-232	194.3	Am-242m	202.3	U-232	212.8	Cf-251	213.9
U-238	206.7	U-233	200.0	Am-243	213.6	U-237	201.9	Th-227	202.2
Pu-239	211.2	U-234	199.5	Cm-243	213.9	Cm-242	216.9	Th-229	202.2
Pu-240	209.7	Np-238	205.8	Cm-244	216.9	Cm-246	216.9		

Figure 4-(a) shows the k_∞ values and corresponding reactivity differences for the different described cases. Overall, the Serpent base case (edep 0) and edep modes 2 and 3 produce nearly identical results, all predicting approximately 400-600 pcm lower reactivity than CASMO5 at 60 MWd/kgU. When the correction for non-critical systems is disabled (ekcorr 0), edep modes 2 and 3 yield around 100 pcm higher reactivity than the corrected cases (ekcorr 1). In contrast, the Serpent with modified heat deposition values (H_i) and edep 1 show different trends. The modified H_i case behaves similarly to the previous Serpent solutions during the BA depletion phase but shows improved agreement with CASMO5 at higher burnups, reducing the difference to about 300 pcm at 60 MWd/kgU. For Serpent edep 1 (with constant 11.0 MeV/fission assumed for capture reactions), the differences at high burnup are even smaller than 300 pcm, but larger discrepancies appear during the depletion of the BAs.

Figure 4. (a) Reactivity differences due to the use of different energy deposition models in Serpent. Differences are relative to CASMO5 reference case. (b) Average energy deposited by fission event for different modes in Serpent.

Figure 4-(b) shows the average energy deposited per fission as a function of burnup for each case. Since the power normalization is kept constant for all cases, one should be aware that this parameter directly affects the rate at which the fuel is consumed, affecting the fuel composition, neutron spectrum, and therefore the multiplication factor. A first observation is that Serpent with modified H_i and edep 1 predict similar trends in the sense that they increase monotonically with burnup, behaviour that is explained due to the appearance of actinides that contribute to fission. Meanwhile CASMO5 and edep modes 2 and 3 better capture the contribution of capture reactions in the BAs, mainly dominated by gadolinium isotopes such as ^{155}Gd and ^{157}Gd , which have relatively high capture release energies of 8.53 and 7.94 MeV per capture, respectively. As these isotopes deplete, the average energy deposition reaches a minimum before increasing again due to the accumulation and fission of newly formed actinides. An initial higher contribution due to capture reactions and better agreement with CASMO5 can be observed when disabling the non-critical correction (ekcorr 0).

Considering integral averages, all Serpent results predict lower energy deposition than CASMO5, as summarized in Table IV. These differences partly explain the systematic reactivity underestimation in the Serpent results, since Serpent must generate more fissions than CASMO5 to maintain the same

power density (24.73 W/g), thereby gradually reducing the fissile isotopic concentration and, consequently, the reactivity. Serpent with modified H_i predicts a higher integrated energy deposition than its base case, remaining approximately 0.5 MeV/fission below CASMO5, which results in better agreement with CASMO5 in terms of reactivity. A similar behavior is observed for Serpent edep 1, which predicts nearly the same integral average value as CASMO5, although in this case the energy deposition is overestimated at low burnups.

Table IV. Integral average of the energy deposition by fission from Figure 4-(b).

CASE	[MeV/fission]	CASE	[MeV/fission]
CASMO5 ERF0	207.46	SERPENT EDEP 2 ecorr 1	205.89
SERPENT EDEP 0	205.50	SERPENT EDEP 2 ecorr 0	206.59
SERPENT EDEP 0 with H_i	206.98	SERPENT EDEP 3 ecorr 1	205.44
SERPENT EDEP 1	207.45	SERPENT EDEP 3 ecorr 0	206.14

Figure 5-(a,c) present the final selected results, including CASMO5 with ERF2 and VESTA in the comparison. For the average energy deposition in VESTA, the isotopes listed in Table III have been considered. VESTA shows good agreement with CASMO5 despite the differences in their energy deposition models. The reason for this agreement is not yet fully clear, but it may stem from differences in specific modelling assumptions, such as the absence of Doppler broadening in VESTA (its libraries are generated at problem-specific defined temperatures), the use of energy-dependent branching ratios, and the scattering thermal law data taken from ENDF/B-VIII.0. CASMO5 ERF2 underestimates the initial energy deposition compared to ERF0, because ERF2 does not take into account problem-specific capture reaction rates as can be seen in Figure 5-(b). Finally, the default Serpent edep 0 model could be improved, without additional computational cost, by using edep 2, this change yields about 200 pcm higher reactivity at 60 MWd/kgU and results in a better agreement against CASMO5.

Figure 5. (a) CASMO5 base case k_∞ and reactivity differences due to the sensitivity analysis. (b) Average energy deposited by capture in [MeV/capture]. (c) Average energy deposited by fission event for the different codes.

Regarding computational resources for Serpent calculations, all simulations were executed on a single Intel Xeon Platinum 8368 CPU using 76 OpenMP threads. No significant differences in wall-clock time were observed among the cases with edep mode 0, 1, and 2, each requiring approximately 6h30m to complete. In contrast, the edep 3 case, which includes coupled neutron-photon transport, required approximately 2d21h50m.

5. CONCLUSION

This work focused on the depletion behavior of a Gd -loaded FA simulated using Serpent, CASMO5, and VESTA, with the objective of quantifying reactivity differences arising from the use of different

energy deposition models. Among the various models, the codes showed very good agreement at fresh fuel composition, but discrepancies of 400-600 pcm emerged during depletion. These differences were primarily observed throughout the BAs depletion phase and at high burnups. In general, Serpent predicted lower reactivity than CASMO5. Part of this underestimation is attributed to the fact that nearly all Serpent cases predict a lower integral average energy deposition compared to CASMO5, which forces Serpent to generate more fissions to maintain constant power, thus accelerating fissile material consumption. CASMO5 and Serpent modes 2 and 3 better captured the contribution of capture reactions during the BAs depletion phase. When the *edepkcorr* was disabled, Serpent showed physical trends similar to CASMO5. Notably, VESTA showed good agreement with CASMO5 despite relying on a simplified constant energy deposition model. Overall, this work has characterized the impact of different energy deposition models on reactivity by maintaining, as much as possible, consistent modelling assumptions across the codes. Nevertheless, other modelling differences that may also influence on the results, such as depletion chains, branching ratios (energy-dependent or not), fission yields, DBRC, etc., have not been fully addressed. Further studies are therefore required to fully understand the origin of the observed discrepancies and determine which methodology provides the most physically accurate representation.

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REFERENCES

- [1] R. Vuiart and et. al. "PRATIC: A soluble-boron-free, pressurized water cooled, SMR core benchmark." *EPJ Nuclear Sci Technol*, **volume 10** (2024).
- [2] G. Prulhière. "D7.1: Specifications of PRATIC fresh core at BOC conditions." *EASI-SMR Project* (2025).
- [3] J. Leppänen and et. al. "The Serpent Monte Carlo code: Status, development and applications in 2013." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 82**, pp. 142–150 (2015).
- [4] R. Ichou, F. L. Dauphin, T. Nicol, C. Carmouze, and F. Estebe. "High Burn-up Code Results Inter-comparison on a Research Reactor Assembly Numerical Benchmark." In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Physics of Reactors (PHYSOR 2024)*. San Francisco, CA, USA (2024).
- [5] R. Tuominen, V. Valtavirta, and J. Leppänen. "New energy deposition treatment in the Serpent 2 Monte Carlo transport code." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 129**, pp. 224–232 (2019).
- [6] M. Chadwick and et. al. "ENDF/B-VII.1 Nuclear Data for Science and Technology: Cross Sections, Covariances, Fission Product Yields and Decay Data." *Nuclear Data Sheets*, **volume 112**(12), pp. 2887–2996 (2011). Special Issue on ENDF/B-VII.1 Library.
- [7] J. Rhodes, K. Smith, and Z. Xu. "CASMO-5 energy release per fission model." (2025).
- [8] Studsvik. "CASMO5. A Fuel Assembly Burnup Program. User's Manual." *Rev 21* (2022).